

The Encountered Challenges in Preparation Process of Kütahya Conservation Plan

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Abstract: The purpose of this work is to find answer to the question of what kind of challenges are encountered in the preparation process of a conservative plan. The preparation process of Conservation Revision Plan of Kütahya Historical City Center has been examined in detail from the perspective of the planning authorities. Case study, literature review, document analysis and in-depth interview methods were used in this study. The fact that the Kütahya Historical Conservation Area does not have a current base map, the absence of archival records giving accurate information on structures in the historic area, negative effects of the master plan decisions on the protection practices taken against the planning area and environment, bureaucratic problems and lack of conservation in public opinion and in stakeholders have been of the difficulties in the preparation process of Kütahya historical city center conservation plan. Research findings give ideas to the competent authorities about the precautions that should be taken before starting the making of a conservation plan and to guide the plan makers. The question of how to obtain a conservation plan that is more qualified and fully responding to needs is an answer to this study.

Keywords: Kütahya, Historical City Centre, Conservation Plan, Challenges.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this work is to find answer to the question of what kind of challenges are encountered in the preparation process of a conservative plan. In this framework, the preparation process of Conservation Revision Plan of Kütahya Historical City Center has been examined in detail from the perspective of the planning authorities. The aim of the study is to give ideas to the competent authorities about the precautions that should be taken before starting the making of a conservation plan and to guide the plan makers. The question of how to obtain a conservation plan that is more qualified and fully responding to needs is an answer to this study.

The article consists of five main sections. In the first part of the article, the purpose, scope and method of study are explained. In the second part, definitions of concepts used in the article that help to understand the research topic are given. In this section, the conservation zone plan is briefly discussed. In the third part of the article, general information about Kütahya Historical City Center that is selected for the field study is given and the characteristics of the area are explained. Also, basic information about the situation of the old conservation plan for the area, reasons for the need for revision of the old plan and basic information about the newly prepared conservation plan are given in this section. In the fourth part of the article, the difficulties encountered in the making process of the Kütahya Conservation Revision Plan are listed from the perspective of the team making the plan based on findings of field work. In the conclusion section, the article is completed by making an evaluation about the preliminary preparations to be made at the point of preparing the conservative development plans which are more qualified and fully responding to needs in the future.

2. Research Methods

Different methods have been applied at different stages of the study. The section in which the conceptual framework is described is based on the literature review. In this context, relevant doctoral dissertations, research reports, laws and regulations, web resources and articles were searched. The general information about Kütahya Historical City Center and

the status of old / new conservation plans belonging to the area have been obtained by conducting on-site field work and analyzing the documents taken from public institutions in Kütahya.

The difficulties encountered in the making process of the Kütahya Conservation Revision Plan were discovered through in-depth interviews with Kütahya Municipality Protection Implementation and Inspection Bureau (KUDEB) and the planning firm that received the making contract of conservation plan. In these interviews, the parties were asked how the need to make a direct Conservative Plan was developed in the city, and what the encountered challenges were in the plan making process, and the subject was thoroughly explored through concrete examples.

3. The Conceptual Framework

This section contains definitions of concepts used in the study and that will help to understand the research topic. In the Law no. 2863 and its regulations in Turkey, the concepts of "cultural assets", "protected area", "urban protected area", "historical protected area", "natural protected area", "archaeological protected area", "conservation" and "conservation development plan" are defined as follows (Official Gazette, 2016):

Cultural Assets: All movable and immovable assets on ground, underground, or under water that have scientific and cultural original value that are related to science, culture, religion and fine arts belonging to prehistoric and historical periods or that have been subject to social life in prehistoric or historical periods are called cultural assets.

Protected Area: Coming up to the day before the prehistoric times, the product of various civilizations, city and city residences reflecting the social, economic, architectural and similar characteristics of the periods they have lived in, the subject of social life in which cultural assets are concentrated or where significant historical events have taken place and with detected nature properties, they are the areas that must be conserved.

Urban Protected Area: Areas showing texture integrity by holding things together, with their urban and regional

characteristics and physical characteristics in terms of architecture and art history, reflecting the way of life to socio-economic, socio-cultural structure of the period and environment.

Historical Protected Area: Areas where important historical events took place in terms of national history and military war history and needed to be protected along with their natural structure.

Natural Protected Area: Areas belonging to prehistoric and historical times in geological periods, exist at overground, underground or under water, needed to be protected in terms of their features and beauties.

Archaeological Protected Area: They are the settlements and fields where include all kinds of cultural assets that reflect the overground, underground and underwater products of the ancient civilizations reaching today from the existence of mankind and the social, economic and cultural characteristics of the periods they have lived.

Conservation: Conservation, maintenance, repair, restoration, function change operations in immovable cultural and natural assets; Maintenance, repair and restoration works in movable cultural assets.

Conservation Development Plan: In designated protected areas according to Law no. 3386 and Law no. 5226 and amended by Law no. 2863, taking into account the area of interaction transition, in order to protect cultural and natural assets in line with the principle of sustainability, including the data of archaeological, historical, natural, architectural, demographic, cultural, socio-economic, ownership and construction, based on field research, on base maps, improving the social and economic structures of the households living in the protected area and the working places, prepared in such a way as to include employment and added value creating strategies, protection principles and conditions of use and restraints of restoration, sanitation, renewal fields and projects, application stages and programs, open space system, pedestrian circulation and vehicle transportation, participatory field management models in accordance with the principles of design of infrastructure facilities, density and parcel design, local ownership, application funding principles, being a whole with objectives, tools, strategies and planning decisions, attitudes, plan notes and explanatory report, these are the plans at the required scale of master and application development plans.

Protected Areas are the areas where immovable cultural and natural assets are preserved and must be protected effectively in the historic environment. With reference to Law no. 3386 and article 51 of amended by Law no. 2863, The High Council of Conservation of Cultural and Natural Heritage (KTVKYK) has divided the protected areas into 3 groups as Urban, Archaeological and Natural Protected Areas. According to Law no. 3386 and 5226 and Law no. 2863 on Protection of Cultural and Natural Assets; The aim of Conservation Plans is to protect cultural and natural assets which are in urban, natural and archaeological protected areas in line with the sustainability principle and transfer them to future generations (Conservation Symposium, 2005). In the situations when both the master and

the application development plans do not respond the needs and its application is a problem, Revision Development Plans are the ones that are obtained after the whole of the plan or most of it is renewed by following the plan construction techniques (Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2013)

What is understood from the concept of “protection” in Turkey, how protection is applied and how protection should be have importance:

In the planning practice of our country, the concept of "conservation development plan" is generally used for the planning of areas registered as natural, historical, archaeological and / or urban protected areas by The Ministry of Culture and Tourism. The concept of “conservation” generally, conservation plan and conservation-oriented plan, evokes an approach that can lead to incorrect results in general planning system and especially in urban planning process. In another sense, classifying urban plans in such a way as to lead to distinctions such as "conservation-oriented" and "non-conservation oriented" may in practice disregard the extent of protection for other plans, or may lead to disconnection of conservation plans from other plans. However, all plan studies to be addressed should be regarded as a conservation plan in essence. (Kiper, 2005).

From past to present, the values that have been tried to be protected within the legal and administrative structure of Turkey have always existed in some way. The deep-rooted point of view within the planning system about the phenomenon of conservation results various problems in the preparation and implementation stages of the conservation plan:

The conservation development plans which are defined as the most effective tools in conservation planning in Turkey, projects and the methods of preparing them and its process, the qualifications of the author and the team have been determined with legal arrangements and obligations have been imposed for the first time in 2004 and after. Thus, new organizations (such as implementation audit offices) and methods (such as field management) have been introduced at the management level to solve urban conservation problems and ensure their feasibility. It is also important to provide transparency and stakeholder participation (such as local government, universities, professional chambers, non-governmental organizations, users) to the protection decisions and especially development planning preparation process and increase the conservation conscious and awareness of community. In spite of these positive developments, to associate conservation plans and development plans at the urban scale and at the legal level and in practice (such as equivalent, synchronicity, mutual interaction) has been denied. (Cinel & Gültekin, 2010)

The importance of the Conservation Plans, which emerged later in Turkey and started to be used as the most effective tool in conservation planning, is newly understood. The issue of how much the previous development plans are related to conservation and how the plans in the future will be integrated with conservation is on the agenda today. In Turkey, the concept of "conservation" has taken place in the urban planning agenda and all the protected areas (archeological and urban

conservation areas) along with the immovable cultural heritage sites (urban conservation areas) remaining within the boundaries of the settlement areas are being evaluated within the city as a whole and integrated development plans has begun to be created. This development is not a legal obligation, but rather a priority initiative and endeavor, especially for urban planners, who are involved in the process. With such kind of plans, the direction and form of urban development are determined and active protection is provided in the areas of immovable cultural heritage. Conservation development plans and reasons for revision of these plans are a matter to be emphasized (Çırak, 2010). Conservation Revision Plans come into play in case of the existing conservation development plans can not meet today's needs. A Conservation Revision Plan, by nature, should be able to overcome the shortcomings of the previous conservation development plan. The importance attached to the master and application development plans for the whole city and conservation plans is also attached to conservation revision plans.

4. Case Study

4.1. General Information about Planning Area

The field survey of this study includes Urban Protected Area, 2nd Degree Archaeological Protected Area, Natural Protected Area and Influence Transition Areas that are inside of Kütahya Central Conservation Development Plan. The size of the area where the field survey was conducted is given below.

Table 1: Sizes of Protected Areas in Central Kütahya

TYPE OF PROTECTED AREA	SIZE (ha)
Urban Protected Area	33,64
Archaeological and Natural Protected Area	33,21
2nd Degree Archaeological Protected Area	5,48
Influence Transition Areas	152,80

Kaynak: (Kütahya Municipality, 2013)

The size of the Urban Protected Area and the Archaeological and Natural Protected Area within the boundaries of the Conservation Plan are almost the same. The most important historic spot in the area is the Kütahya Castle and its surroundings. The castle is located in the Natural Protected Area which covers a large part of the old city center of Kütahya. The site with the minimum size within the planning area is the Second Degree Archaeological Protected Area. Within the boundaries of the Conservation Plan, there are two urban protected areas and two archaeological protected areas, one as the first degree and one as the second degree. These protected areas are located within the boundaries of City's Influence Transition Area (Figure 1). The border of Influence Transition Area also constitutes the border of Conservation Revision Plan.

Figure 1: Boundaries of Protected Areas and Influence Transition Area in Central Kütahya (Central Kütahya Conservation Development Plan Research Report, 2013)

The first decision regarding the old city center of Kütahya to be a protected area was given on 14.07.1979. However, the first protected area boundary was partially amended after the first registered list of buildings was established on 18.11.1980. The borders of the protected area within the historic city center of Kütahya was restored with the decision of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, the High Council of Immovable Cultural and Natural Heritage (TKTVKYK) dated 13.07.1984 and number 292. According to this decision, on condition that the protection of the immovable cultural assets that are worth preserving, the small protected area determined by the High Council of the Real Estate Antiquities and Monuments was removed and the large protected area was divided into two separate pieces and the area between the old and new protected area boundaries was determined as transition area. Later, the area, defined as the Archaeological and Natural Protected Area in the conservation development plan approved by the decision of TKTVKYK dated 17.07.1987 and numbered 3552, was registered as a first degree archeological protected area by the decision of The Conservation Board of Eskişehir Cultural and Natural Assets, dated 16.03.2011 and numbered 1384. So its quality and degree was changed. Another recent decision on the borders of conservation area is the regulation on the 2nd Degree Archaeological Site Boundary in line with the decision of the Regional Board for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage of Kütahya dated 03.10.2011 and numbered 28. Accordingly, Hıdırlık Tepesi was registered as the Archaeological and Natural Conservation Area with the decision of TKTVKYK dated 17.07.1987 and numbered 3552, but due to the absence of the archaeological conservation area criterion, with the decision of The Conservation Board of Eskişehir Cultural and Natural Assets dated 27.09.2001 and numbered 1608, It was first declared as the 3rd Degree Natural Conservation Area and then 2nd Degree Archaeological Conservation Area with the decision of the same Board dated 26.01.2007 and numbered 1684. The archaeological remains found in the new excavations in this area led to the alteration and extension of the archaeological protected area boundary (Central Kütahya Conservation Development Plan Research Report, 2013).

The urban, archeological and natural protected areas in Kütahya emphasize the historical and cultural significance of the city center, indicating that the city has a tourism potential. The residential structure and traditional commercial units in the

conservation areas reflect the architectural, cultural and historical accumulation that has reached today from the historical period of Kütahya. Kütahya Castle, which is one of the most important focus and impression points of the city, is one of the oldest historical areas of the city and remains within the natural and archeological protected areas. Kütahya Castle, which belongs to the Byzantine Period and is one of the most important cultural heritages of civilization, is a monumental historical artifact which stands out with its uses such as bastions, walls, doors, materials, architecture and today's fountains, restaurants and mosques.

Because of the lack of an approved environmental plan in Kütahya province, it can not be mentioned about the contradiction or harmony between the upper-scale and lower-scale plan decisions. The most active part of planning within the provincial borders is the area of Kütahya municipal boundaries. The most important problem experienced in this region is that the municipal boundaries are so small therefore urban developments can not be controlled, supervised or regulated from one hand. While there are not many natural thresholds that limit the development of the planning area in Kütahya city, it can be said that the Urban Protected Areas in the central district and the Natural and Archeological Protected Area in which the fortress and its surroundings are located affect the decision of location selection in the city and these decisions are also determinant in the formation of the urban macro form.

4.2. Reasons for the Revision of the Old Conservation Development Plan

The first Kütahya Historical City Center Conservation Plan made in 1980 has now become unable to respond to today's needs. A number of plan modifications were made on this plan. In conservation legislation, too many changes have taken place over the past 30 years. For this reason, it has been necessary to revise the existing protection plan. Within the boundaries of the Revision Conservation Plan, there are a total of 466 registered monuments; 147 monumental buildings, 287 examples of civil architecture and 32 natural assets. "The Construction Work of Kütahya (Center) Protected Areas and Influence Transition Areas Revision Conservation Plan" which had been tendered for a contract by Kütahya Municipality was taken on 20 February 2012 by the Consultancy Service Procurement Method within the scope of the Public Procurement Authority Specification. Under the terms of the tender, it was envisaged that the Revision Conservation Plan to be completed within 240 working days. An experienced Planning Bureau (private company), which has been operating in the sector since 1992 and provides planning, consultancy services to municipalities, special provincial administrations and ministries, has taken the work of making plans. The planning bureau has completed 15 conservation development plans in the past. It carries out the conservation plan of 15 different areas including Kütahya at the same time. The team formed to carry out the Kütahya Conservation Development Plan project consists of seven urban planners, one restorer architect, two art historians, one archaeologist, one sociologist and one landscape architect. The Contractor company has undertaken to the employer Kütahya Municipality to gradually complete the plan construction work within the framework of a certain work program.

The reasons leading to the revision of the existing Conservation Plan are summarized under three headings in the most general sense. These are:

- The existing conservation development plan was made in the 1980s,
- There have been some changes in the legislation so far, and
- There are 132 plan modifications made in the planning area up to day time.

The number of registered cultural assets that existed in 1987, when the First Conservation Plan was prepared and approved, has changed considerably so far. The increase in the number of registered buildings is one of the basic reasons for plan revision. Over time, the positions of the registered and conserved structures in the approved plan have made it necessary to renew the plan decisions. It is another important reason for the revision of the plan that the first conservation plan dates back to old times, can not respond to today's needs, and there are many changes in the existing area as well as legislation. The existence of 132 plan modifications made to date in the field of planning and making many changes in the field reveals that the plan editing is damaged. These changes have had a number of implications for both the conserved area and conserved cultural and natural assets. With the amendments of the plan, many works were registered and included in the scope of protection, along with this, the registration on many works was also removed and removed from the scope of conservation. The constant increase in the number of amendments has also taken place in the revision reasons.

When we look at the decisions regarding transport and access in the old Kütahya Historical City Center Conservation Plan, which is the subject of the revision, it is seen that the functional importance and hierarchies of the existing road networks that have been formed in the city have been preserved to a great extent even today. While the width of Lala Hüseyin Pasha, Hisar Ahmed and Meydan Streets was enlarged in the plan, these streets are narrower today due to the fact that important historical buildings constitute obstacles. Although, in the old plan, it has been decided to close many narrow roads that do not allow the vehicle traffic in, this traffic application can not be realized today. It has been found that the first conservation plan decisions can only be partially implemented in 30 years. Especially in commercial areas, unplanned interventions have been made and roads have been expanded and new roads have caused some historical buildings to disappear. It has been found that the old conservation development plan contains positive elements to protect the decisions taken for transport and access, but today these decisions can not be fully implemented. Attention has been paid to the protection of existing facade lines of the roads in which the registered building groups are located in the old plan. Especially in the characteristic forms of street silhouette, it is proposed that the existing front lines indicated on the plan are to be obeyed in large proportion and in case of necessity, the front lines are withdrawn in areas with certain characteristic features. However, Indicating that it is open to consideration of benefit and damage balance in the application decisions for the facade protection in the plan, that is, leaving the open parts for the

comments in the old plan has caused some disagreements over time in practice. Eventually, there have been deteriorations in traditional texture and street facades. The obligation to take special care of areas that forms texture with unique street facade, as well as the protection of registered cultural assets, was one of the reasons for establishing a new conservation revision plan.

Decisions on the use of trade in the former conservation development plan were made in a way that is not contrary to the traditional texture and with respect to its real boundaries. In the direction of old plan decisions, ground floors of buildings are usually divided into small commercial activities, handicrafts and service sector. It is decided to keep away from the intensification that would disrupt the traditional character of the historic commercial structures such as inn, covered bazaar, small shops, etc. located in and around Pekmezpazararı Caddesi. The development of new commercial activities was supported in Cumhuriyet and Hürriyet Streets and the newly opened Kıbrıs Street. The trade lines defined in the old plan decisions have become reality today and The historic trade center continued to maintain its vitality. However, the physical units in the historic center, which still maintain its presence today, are more likely to sustain small commercial activities in the traditional structure. The commercial activities at the center of Kütahya now spread over a wider area. Especially, Cumhuriyet, Hürriyet and Kıbrıs Streets and Tahıl pazarı, Kavafılar, Mısır Çarşısı and Saraçhane Streets that are in the historical trade center and Pekmez Pazarı Street are main lines spreading commercial activity. Innovative commercial activities in the field of planning are generally located in the city center and has not entered much into the newly developing residential areas and the residential areas that have intensely traditional features. Commercial activities generally developed on certain lines in the direction of newly developed residential and socio-cultural areas, showing partial dispersion in some areas except for linear and regional focuses. Although it is not very common in the area, the spreading of these dispersions in a way that will create a new texture contrary to the existing texture, moreover, the development of high-rise building proposals despite the traditional texture and the lack of transit links between traditional trade and innovative trade areas have been among the justifications of the revision of the conservation development plan.

The monumental cultural assets within the planning area, before the first conservation plan, were registered and protected by the decision of the High Council of Immovable Cultural and Natural Assets, dated 18.01.1980 and numbered A-2087. The number of monumental buildings registered after this date is rather small Most of these monumental cultural assets in the area of planning have reached today and the restored structures are also used with original functions or new functions. There are some monumental structures in the area that are not registered, have incomplete restoration or have never been restored. For the conservation, registration and restoration of these constructions, it is also necessary to go through a revision of the conservation plan. The increase in the number of conserved artifacts over the years, the increase in importance attached to conservation, that is, conservation awareness, is one of the reasons for the revision of the conservative plan.

The number of building registers that are samples of the civil architecture within the boundaries of the first conservation plan and have a decisive role in the decision about plans has experienced significant changes over the years. According to the results obtained from the decisions of the Conservation Board, it is seen that the majority of examples of civil architecture were registered with the decisions dated 18.01.1980 and numbered A-2087 and also dated 13.07.1984 and numbered 292, there are very few structures registered as examples of civil architecture in recent history. According to the decision of The High Council of Immovable Cultural and Natural Assets, dated 17.07.1987 and numbered 3552, the constructions of civil architecture samples in Kütahya center are evaluated as group registered structure. When examining the registration decisions for civil architectural examples, it is seen that most of the structures in the planning area are registered with the decision of the board in 1980, with the additions and edits made in the following years, some cultural assets are deducted from registration and some historical structures are registered as cultural assets that must be conserved. It draws attention to the fact that some examples of civil architecture registered in the direction of the decision dated 18.01.1980 and numbered A-2087, their registers have been removed in the following years but some of them have recently re-registered as cultural assets that must be conserved. In this case, it is seen that many examples of registered civil architecture are deducted from the register, and many works are re-registered. Change in number of civil architecture examples constitute another reason for revision.

The process that started with the change of the users living in the urban conservation areas, brought about the change in the physical constructions in the area over time. The change in the user profile of historical buildings has led to significant variations in traditional texture. On the other hand, motor vehicle traffic has increased in the region over the years, which has led to the transformation of some lines, which are intensified in traditional trade, into a street. Following the expansion of the road, the number of storeys along the street has been increased. Floor increments that were allowed in the first conservation plan and incompatible with building heights of the traditional texture in the area were supported by master development plan decisions and new buildings that damage the high-rise traditional texture have started in the area of planning. In the first conservation plan, in the areas other than the sections where 2-3 storey constructions are recommended, the adjacent order in the master building plan and that the decision to build up to the 8 storey were taken has caused significant deterioration in the historical texture. It has become imperative to take measures to revise the conservation plan in order to prevent further damage to historic texture, to ensure integrity within the area, and to regulate relations with the surrounding area of the historic area.

In the first conservation plan, the influence transition area is included in the protected area method. The fact that the influence transition area in the plan is very large and conservation in the area is as effective as the protected area have made implementation difficult. Since the management and control of large area conservation gets difficult, the need to reorganize the influence transition area boundary has arisen. That inadequate depths and facade lengths, presence of floor disputes within the same block, some uncertainties in the plan, base map is not up to date, the old plan is not in line with the

new conservation legislation and the plan language, the decisions taken over the years in the field of conservation do not support each other, the historical center is treated as disconnected from the whole of the city, problems experienced in practice required the revision of the conservation plan.

5. Research Findings: The Difficulties in the Preparation Process of the Conservation Plan

In this section, the problems encountered during the preparation process of the Central Kütahya Conservation Revision Plan have been explored by evaluating the literature survey, field research, document analysis and data obtained from in-depth interviews. In the study of the Conservation Revision Plan prepared for Kütahya Historical City Center, the experienced difficulties have been researched between the employer Kütahya Municipality and the contractor and plan maker company in the process started from the signing of the contract up to the last delivery of the conservation plan. When the former Conservation Plan is examined, it can be seen that the approaches towards conservation are positive but some of the plan decisions can not be performed due to the contradictions with the Master Plan. For this reason, some problems are encountered in practice today such as road expansion, protection of street silhouette, that height of floors are incompatible with traditional texture. The difficulties experienced during the preparation process of Kütahya Historical City Conservation Plan are listed below under specific headings:

▪ That Kütahya Historical City Center does not have a contemporary map

The first and biggest problem in the preparation process of the Kütahya Historical City Conservation Plan has been the lack of current maps. The first conservation plan prepared in 1987 was based on the existing map of 1957. So the revision plan study had to do a long-term land survey in order to eliminate the inventory deficiency first. During this process, all registered buildings were recorded to new pre-existing maps, situations that were contrary to the old cadastral map and the conservation plan were determined, new protected area boundaries were processed correctly with current pre-existing maps. This lack of initial accountability has resulted in considerable time and labor loss in the planning process.

▪ Lack of archival records that provide accurate information about the historical area

Another problem was that the archive records belonging to registered monumental cultural assets structures and registered civil architecture examples buildings in Kütahya Historical City Center were inadequate / unhealthy and contain outdated information. The fact that the number of registered buildings in the historical center has increased and decreased in number over the years and that the archive records of these changes have not been kept properly have caused serious difficulties in reaching the latest information on the protected structure, especially newly registered. Therefore, at the beginning of the planning period, it was obliged to recreate the ownership and registration information belonging to all the historical registered structures remaining in the planning area.

▪ Negative effect on the protection practices of master plan decisions taken for planning area and environment

The master development plan decisions taken regarding the areas other than the protected area in the old city center of Kütahya have caused a structuring pressure in the conservation area. The fact that the development plans related to the Kütahya city center are not prepared in an integrated manner, that is, they are not related to each other, constituted a serious problem. In the master plan, on the wall of the conservation area, high-rise and adjoining buildings were proposed and this situation resulted a structuring pressure on the conservation area. In the old conservation development plan, in the areas other than the sections where 2-3 storey constructions were recommended, the adjacent order in the master building plan and the constructions up to 8 storey were recommended. So, in the process of preparing the new conservation plan, a developing perspective, instead of guarding, dominated all stakeholders. This situation led that the parties spiritedly express their demands which would destroy the integrity of the historical texture and its surroundings, thus, it became difficult to make complementary protection plans for the area to be protected.

▪ The bureaucratic problems

That the scientific background and the inventory system is incomplete and not updated, the lack of language unity among the experts of the subject, the lack of technical staff and organization with sufficient experience and knowledge in conservation and problems arising from the lack of coordination between institutions on conservation have been major problems in the preparation process of planning. The long duration of work in public institutions brought about time losses in the planning process. That bureaucratic procedures take time has made it difficult to revise the plan while delaying the conservation initiatives. After the conservation plan was prepared, it was sent to the approval process and had to be waited too long for the plan approval. The absence of a time limit for the acceptance and approval of the conservation development plan has extended the approval process, which has become a major problem for planners and implementers. In addition, the area subject to the conservation development plan remains within the borders of Kütahya Municipality in terms of local government authorities. Another organizational structure that can be characterized as administrative authority within the urban boundaries is the Regional Council for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage, which is affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism. However, due to the presence of archaeological protected areas in Kütahya Castle and in the south of the area, Kütahya Museum Directorate is also among the authorized institutions in the conservation area. The responsibility and authority of many different institutions in the conservation area has led to administrative problems both in the plan making phase and in the implementation phase as a whole as regards to protection decisions.

▪ Poor awareness of conservation among public and stakeholders

In the process of making of the new Conservation Plan, the perspective of city people, stakeholders and politics in terms of development, not conservation, has made it more difficult to make ideal plan decisions. The majority of the population

living in the area covered by the conservation plan study is those migrating from rural areas. This section is in the middle and lower group in terms of socio-economic structure and income level. Domestic families with high socio-economic level and living in the region have abandoned this area, which has been exposed to aging in time, and poor families with low socio-economic status have settled in these vacated houses. In this process, the user profile of the area has constantly changed, causing it to turn into a transition zone rather than a settled location. The fact that new property owners or users both have low income levels and low level of education and that they are not sufficiently conscious of the historic conservation issue has raised the problem of the lack of full public participation in the conservation plan preparation process. When the public tended to refrain from participating in social surveys, plan decisions that were not fully fed from reality and locality were taken. The extent to which public participation has not been achieved at the desired level is in some way related to how the participation meetings are held, the contents of the meetings, how participation is tried to be achieved and whether the meeting number is sufficient. Since the public participation process is not well managed, there is no public pressure to direct the plan construction process correctly and effectively, and there is no mutual healthy exchange of views between the plan makers and the public. It has been determined that the conservation consciousness is very weak in the people who live in Kütahya Historical City Center and use this place. The planning process has not progressed democratically enough for this reason. In order to be able to create protection consciousness, it has been seen that there is a need to inform the public of the latest legal arrangements about private work, time and protection.

It was desired to conduct a survey during the preparation of the Conservation Plan, but very few citizens participated in this survey. The basis of this problem is also that the stakeholders can not be organized and that citizens do not have enough knowledge about the region. Therefore, public participation was low, the efficiency of the survey study could not be obtained at the desired level, and the practical knowledge of the people could not be acquired into the plan. Those who are most affected by conservation decisions are of course living in the area declared as a protected area. Residents of the neighborhood are directly affected by decisions and practices in the planning process. Since public participation was not provided, the social dimension in the planning process had to be ignored to a certain extent. The place where the plan is made is a social center, so everyday life continues in the region. However, the attitudes, perceptions, and perspectives of people living in the region have not been taken into the center of planning in the planning process. It is therefore difficult for the protection plan to be a functioning plan.

6. Conclusion

Planning has existed in every period of human history. Planning is also a convenient and necessary tool for conservation actions at the same time. It is understood that the comprehensive rational planning concept, which is a judge in Turkey for many years, has negative effects on the conservation initiatives. In the preparation of the conservation plan, the inability to access accurate and comprehensive spatial information and the fact that decision-making and control mechanisms are not well managed has emerged as an important problem. In addition, it is understood that the view and

mentality of the competent institutions, the people of the city and the stakeholders to preserve the history is a subject that should be specially considered. In the plans that historical and cultural protection is the primary objective, on how to truly protect the values of cultural and natural beings should be discussed more. In the preparation process of Kütahya's historic city center conservation plan, public awareness of the city and its stakeholders has been weak, public participation has not been sufficiently achieved, So this has partially weakened the applicability dimension of the plan.

Since the 1950s, Kütahya has been in a continuous and rapid movement and the changes and deteriorations experienced in the physical environment in this direction have adversely affected the protected areas especially in the city. Today, the only means of protection of cultural and natural assets, in other words, preservation of historical, cultural and natural environments, appears to be "conservation plans". Conservation plan has firstly entered to the agenda of Kütahya in the 1980s. However, the place and role of the plan in the city as a whole has not been fully defined, and the urban conservation area has been tried to be planned alone. Conservation plans should be prepared in close relation to all other plans that concern the same region. It has been determined that there is a great need for plan studies that complement each other and that integrate with the protected area. The preparation and approval of conservation plans alone does not mean the protection of cultural and natural assets. The study found that the implementation phase of conservation plans is at least as important as the plan preparation phase. It has come to the conclusion that the prepared conversation plans should be applicable and active plans, not passive ones. This study has revealed that it can not serve exactly the purpose of conservation plans prepared to cover only the historical region without considering the interaction with the whole city. Because there are conflicting and conflicting decisions about the intertwined areas in the city, which adversely affect the conservation initiatives.

It is seen that the physical, social and economic problems observed in the historical city centers throughout Turkey are also experienced in the historical city center of Kütahya. That there are many types of protected areas within the boundaries of the conservation development plan, and that the area of influence transition area is very wide have made the protection efforts the most difficult. That too many institutions have a say in the conservation area makes the emergence of language and thought unity difficult and makes the control mechanism unhealthy and ineffective. Numerous changes in the legislation, numerous reconstruction plans, incomplete implementation of transportation decisions in the current plans, inability to implement land use decisions due to lack of support from the people, increase in the number of cultural assets and examples of civil architecture in the registered monumental natural assets are the leading reasons for the revision of the conservation development plan. It has been determined that the road system in the old city center of Kütahya is at a point that can not function today and decisions regarding transportation and access to the conservation development plans can not be implemented in the city. Multi-storey buildings, rising in and around the old city center create a negative pressure on the conservation development plan, making it difficult to reach the plan goals. There are many monumental structures in Kütahya's old city center that their restorations have not finished yet or

have never been restored. In addition to these, there are also new registered or unregistered buildings. The lack of information on the nature of the historic structures and on the registration status has made the conservation plan preparation process difficult and delayed. It has emerged that a conservation plan should not be initiated before a healthy inventory record of historic buildings has been created in a protected area. The study also revealed that each plan had a lifetime.

Within the scope of the study, the difficulties encountered during the preparation process for a conservation development plan were identified and the conservation plans to be carried out after this were made more conscious. Historical surroundings provide a bridge to the future from the past. The fact that the Kütahya Historical Conservation Area does not have a current base map, the absence of archival records giving accurate information on structures in the historic area, negative effects of the master plan decisions on the protection practices taken against the planning area and environment, bureaucratic problems and lack of conservation in public opinion and in stakeholders have been of the difficulties in the preparation process of Kütahya historical city center conservation plan. These difficulties are all interconnected difficulties. It is understood within the scope of this study that the conservation development plans should be followed by a well thought area action and management plan.

Another problem in the making process of the Kütahya conservation plan was the lack of widespread conservation consciousness, inability of the people to be organized and their participation in conservation processes. Due to this problem it is difficult to prepare a viable conservation plan in the city. If protection awareness is established, the public will participate in the plan construction process. If city people are organized in terms of protection, if more effective and innovative methods are developed to achieve public participation, and social analysis and communication are attached more importance, then, conservation plans can be converted into more feasible plans. The issue of participation is a challenge that can be overcome by meeting stakeholder participation. During these meetings, people's awareness of conservation can be increased. The best practitioners of the prepared plans are the people living in the planning area. Conservation consciousness can be created by increasing the number of meetings to be held in the planning process, before and after the plan construction, regular training and informing, and organizing communication campaigns. Findings within the scope of this study are guiding the development of more successful conservation plans and the progress of the conservation processes more smoothly.

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